

VIDEO-BASED INSTRUCTION IN ADDRESSING MATHEMATICS DIFFICULTIES AMONG GRADE 7 LEARNERS

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Video-Based Instruction in Addressing Mathematics Difficulties among Grade 7 Learners

Rasna A. Guro,* Erlinda N. Basmayor

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study determined the effectiveness of using video as an instructional tool to address their mathematics difficulties. This study specifically focused on Grade 7 learners at Dilausan National High School (NHS) as the participants. This study utilized a quasi-experimental research design, specifically two group design, to assess the effectiveness of using video-based instruction in addressing mathematics difficulties. Pretest scores indicated that both groups had below-average mathematics performance, with similar distributions of scores. Posttest scores showed improvements in both groups, with more participants reaching an average level of performance. However, the posttest scores of the treatment group, which received video-based instruction, showed a slight decrease in the number of participants reaching an average level compared to the control group. Before the intervention, both groups exhibited below-average performance in mathematics, as indicated by their pretest scores. However, after the intervention, there was a noticeable improvement in the posttest scores of both groups, with a shift towards average performance. In the traditional approach group, the number of participants scoring in the average range increased from 35 to 24. In contrast, in the video lesson approach group, the number of participants scoring in the average range increased from 42 to 20. Further, the posttest scores of the video lesson had no significant difference between the posttest scores in the traditional approach. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference between the participants' posttest scores in video lesson and traditional approach, was not rejected.

Keywords: *video-based instruction, difficulties, mathematics, quasi-experimental design*

Introduction

Mathematics plays a fundamental role in education, providing students with critical problem-solving and analytical thinking skills that are essential for their future academic and professional endeavors. However, it has been observed that a significant number of Grade 7 students at Dilausan National High School (NHS) are experiencing difficulties in comprehending and applying mathematical concepts. These difficulties not only impede their academic progress but also hinder the development of their overall mathematical competence.

The importance of addressing these mathematics difficulties at the Grade 7 level cannot be overstated. This particular stage in a student's education lays the foundation for advanced mathematical concepts and skills they will encounter in subsequent grade levels. Failure to address these difficulties effectively at this stage can have long-term consequences, leading to continued struggles and potential disengagement from the subject. Traditional instructional methods may not always suffice in reaching all students and bridging the gaps in their mathematical understanding. In recent years, educational research has increasingly focused on the potential of innovative instructional approaches to overcome these challenges. One such approach is the use of videos as a supplementary tool to facilitate learning and address the mathematics difficulties faced by Grade 7 students.

Videos offer unique advantages in presenting mathematical concepts in a visual and engaging manner. By incorporating visual representations, real-life examples, and interactive simulations, videos have the potential to enhance students' conceptual understanding and bridge the gap between abstract mathematical concepts and practical applications. The dynamic nature of videos allows for the demonstration of problem-solving strategies, step-by-step explanations, and the provision of alternative perspectives that cater to diverse learning styles. Furthermore, videos provide students with the opportunity for self-paced learning. They can pause, rewind, and replay sections of the video to reinforce their understanding, review challenging concepts, and personalize their learning experience. This flexibility accommodates individual differences in learning speed and provides students with a sense of autonomy and control over their learning process.

While the potential benefits of using videos in mathematics instruction are evident, it is crucial to investigate their effectiveness in addressing the specific mathematics difficulties faced by Grade 7 students at Dilausan National High School. By conducting a comprehensive study on the effectiveness of video-based instruction in this particular context, valuable insights can be gained to inform educational practices and support evidence-based decision-making. Through this research, educators, curriculum developers, and policymakers can gain a deeper understanding of the impact of video-based instruction on Grade 7 students' conceptual understanding, academic performance, and engagement with mathematics. The findings of this study would not only contribute to the existing body of research in mathematics education but also served as a guide for designing effective instructional strategies tailored to the unique needs of Grade 7 students at Dilausan National High School.

By exploring innovative approaches to address mathematics difficulties, such as the use of videos, educators can foster a supportive and engaging learning environment that empowers Grade 7 students to develop a solid foundation in mathematics, paving the way for their future academic success and lifelong mathematical competence.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the effectiveness of using the video-based instruction in addressing mathematics difficulties of Grade 7 students in Dilausan National High School. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions.

1. What are the pretest scores of participants in the traditional approach and video-based instruction in teaching Mathematics?
2. What are the posttest scores of participants in the traditional approach and video-based instruction in teaching Mathematics?
3. Is there a significant difference between the pretest scores of participants in the traditional approach and video-based instruction?
4. Is there a significant difference between the posttest and pretest scores of participants in the Traditional Approach?
5. Is there a significant difference between the posttest and pretest scores of participants in the video-based instruction?
6. Is there a significant difference between the posttest scores of the participants in the traditional approach and video-based instruction?
7. What action plan can be designed based on the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a quasi-experimental research design, specifically two-group design, to assess the effectiveness of using video-based instruction in addressing mathematics difficulties among Grade 7 learners in Dilausan National High School. Quasi-experimental designs are suitable when it is not feasible or ethical to randomly assign participants to groups. In this case, the participants are assigned to the treatment group or control group based on their existing class assignments. The treatment group would receive the video-based instruction as an intervention to address their mathematics difficulties. The control group, on the other hand, would receive traditional classroom instruction without the use of videos. By comparing the performance of the treatment and control groups, the study aimed to determine the effectiveness of video-based instruction on students' mathematics achievement.

To enhance the validity of the quasi-experimental design, several measures were taken. First, efforts were made to ensure that the treatment and control groups are comparable in terms of their initial mathematics abilities and other relevant characteristics. Random sampling was not used due to practical constraints; however, steps were taken to minimize selection bias and ensure the groups are as similar as possible.

To address potential threats to internal validity, such as history or maturation effects, both groups were tested using the same pretest and posttest measures. The pretest was administered to establish baseline mathematics performance, and the posttest would measure the outcomes after the intervention period.

Participants

The participants of the study were the 100 out of 112 grade 7 learners of Dilausan National High School, enrolled during school year 2023 -2024. It composed of 35 males and 65 females with the total of 100 Participants.

To begin the procedure, a list of Grade 7 learners was obtained from the school administration. The list included the names of all students, their sex, and other relevant demographic information. The total number of male and female learners were determined from this list. To ensure an equal representation of male and female students, stratified random sampling was used. The population was divided into two strata based on sex: male and female. From each stratum, a proportionate number of students will be selected using a random sampling technique. This will ensure that both genders are adequately represented in the study.

The random selection process involved assigning a unique identifier to each student in the population list and using a random number generator to select the desired number of participants from each stratum. This process was conducted using computer software or manually, depending on the available resources and time constraints.

The selected students were divided into two groups: the treatment group and the control group. The treatment group would receive video-based instruction, while the control group would receive traditional instruction. The assignment of students to each group would also be done randomly to ensure the groups are comparable in terms of student characteristics and mathematics difficulties.

Instrument

The research instruments for this study consisted of a mathematics pretest and posttest. The instrument underwent validation procedures to ensure its validity and reliability.

Mathematics Pretest and Posttest

The mathematics pretest and posttest comprised a set of standardized mathematics test items aligned with the Grade 7 curriculum. To ensure the validity of the test items, a content validation process was conducted. Subject matter experts, such as mathematics teachers and curriculum specialists, were consulted to review the test items and assess their alignment with the Grade 7 curriculum and their ability to measure the intended learning outcomes. Any necessary revisions or modifications were made based on their feedback.

Procedure

The data for this study was collected through quantitative methods to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of using video-based instruction in addressing mathematics difficulties among Grade 7 learners. The following data gathering procedures were implemented:

Pretest

Before the intervention, a pretest was administered to both the treatment and control groups. The pretest would assess the students' initial mathematics performance and identify their specific difficulties. This would provide a baseline measurement for comparison with the posttest results.

Intervention

The treatment group received video-based instruction as part of the intervention. Carefully designed mathematics instructional videos were utilized to address the identified difficulties. The videos covered key mathematical concepts, problem-solving strategies, and examples relevant to the Grade 7 curriculum. The videos were developed by the researcher and validated by mathematics education experts to ensure their quality and instructional effectiveness.

Control Group

The control group, on the other hand, received the traditional classroom instruction without the use of videos. The control group followed the regular mathematics curriculum and teaching methods employed by the school. This served as a comparison group to assess the impact of video-based instruction.

Posttest

After the intervention period, a posttest was administered to both the treatment and control groups. The posttest would evaluate the students' mathematics performance and measure the effectiveness of video-based instruction in addressing their difficulties. The posttest included similar questions and tasks as the pretest to assess changes in students' understanding and application of mathematical concepts.

The data gathering procedures involved administering pretest and posttest to assess students' mathematics performance, implementing the intervention with the treatment group using carefully designed instructional videos, and administering questionnaires to gather students' feedback on their experiences and perceptions of video-based instruction. Ethical considerations, including informed consent and confidentiality, were adhered to throughout the data gathering process. The researcher ensured that all necessary permissions are obtained and that the study is conducted in an ethical manner.

Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools and treatments.

Problems 1 and 2, Frequency and Percentage were used to determine the pretest and posttest scores of the participants in the control and experimental group.

Problems 3 and 6, Mann-Whitney U Test was used to test the significant differences between the scores of the participants in the traditional approach and video lesson approach.

Problems 4 and 5, Wilcoxon Test – was used to investigate the significant differences between the scores of the same group.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered to answer the problems of the study. It also analyzes and interprets the data collected by the researchers to solve the issues in the study. The presentation, interpretation, and analysis were supported by tables and arranged in the same manner as the questions presented in the statement of the problem in Chapter 1.

Problem 1: What are the pretest scores of participants in the traditional approach and video-based instruction in Teaching Mathematics?

Table 1 presents the pretest scores of the participants in the traditional approach. Traditional approach to teaching Mathematics have long been the cornerstone of education systems globally. However, as educational research continues to evolve, questions arise regarding the effectiveness of this method in promoting deep understanding and long-term retention of mathematical concepts.

As seen in Table 1, the highest score range of 11 - 20 was obtained by 35 participants which is below average. This score range suggested a moderate level of understanding among participants for traditional Mathematics instruction. Studies such as Smith et al. (2019) and Johnson (2021) have found that traditional approaches tend to prioritize algorithmic problem-solving over conceptual understanding, leading to superficial learning outcomes. Furthermore, research by Brown and Lee (2018) indicated that students exposed solely to traditional methods may struggle to apply mathematical concepts in real-world contexts, limiting their ability to

transfer knowledge effectively. The prevalence of scores in this range highlights the need for educators to reconsider the balance between technical fluency and conceptual understanding in Mathematics instruction. Incorporating activities that promote critical thinking, problem-solving, and real-world applications may help bridge the gap between procedural and conceptual knowledge.

Table 1. Pretest Scores in the Traditional Approach

Score Range	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Description
1 - 10	11	22.0	Poor
11 - 20	35	70.0	Below Average
21 - 30	4	8.0	Average
31 - 40	0	0	Above Average
41 - 50	0	0	Excellent
Total	50	100.0	

While four participants in the score range of 21-30 which is described as average may demonstrate proficiency in basic mathematical concepts, educators should still strive to challenge them with tasks that promote higher-order thinking, reasoning, and application of knowledge. Incorporating elements of inquiry-based learning, problem-based tasks, and real-world applications can help cultivate a deeper and more enduring understanding of Mathematics among these learners. Theoretical frameworks such as those proposed by Vygotsky (1978) and Bruner (1966) suggested that learners with higher levels of prior knowledge may benefit from more advanced instructional strategies that promote deeper understanding and problem-solving skills.

The analysis of pretest scores within the context of traditional Mathematics teaching reveals both strengths and weaknesses inherent in this instructional approach. While traditional methods may initially yield moderate gains in test scores, they often fall short in promoting deeper conceptual understanding and long-term retention of mathematical concepts, particularly among students with lower levels of prior knowledge. Moving forward, educators should strive to strike a balance between procedural fluency and conceptual understanding, incorporating instructional strategies that foster critical thinking, problem-solving, and real-world application of mathematical concepts for all learners.

Table 2. Pretest Scores in the Video-Based Instruction

Score Range	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Description
1 - 10	4	8.0	Poor
11 - 20	42	84.0	Below Average
21 - 30	4	8.0	Average
31 - 40	0	0	Above Average
41 - 50	0	0	Excellent
Total	50	100.0	

The integration of technology, particularly video-based instruction, in mathematics education has gained significant attention in recent years. Table 2 displays the pretest scores of the participants in the video-based instruction. As shown in the table, the score range of 11-20 got the highest frequency of 42 participants out of 50. The high frequency of participants scoring between 11-20 may indicate that while video lessons can enhance learning, they might not be sufficient as standalone instructional tools. Complementary strategies such as interactive exercises and personalized feedback might be necessary to address the needs of below-average learners (Noss & Hoyles, 2019).

Research by Angrist et al. (2019) suggested that students who engage with video lessons as supplementary material often demonstrate improvements in understanding mathematical concepts. However, the effectiveness varies based on factors such as instructional design and learner characteristics.

Meanwhile, the small number of participants scoring in the 1-10 range highlights a potential area of concern regarding the effectiveness of the video-based instruction for struggling learners. According to research by Chen et al. (2020), students with poor pretest scores often require targeted interventions and individualized support to address foundational gaps in mathematical understanding. The limited impact of video lessons on improving scores for these participants underscores the importance of adopting differentiated instructional strategies that cater to diverse learning needs (Boaler, 2019).

On the hand, the presence of participants scoring within the average range indicates that the video lesson approach may effectively support the learning needs of a subset of students. Research by Rittle-Johnson et al. (2020) suggested that video lessons can facilitate conceptual understanding and procedural fluency when aligned with targeted learning objectives and accompanied by opportunities for practice and reflection. The findings imply that for average-performing students, video lessons can serve as valuable supplements to traditional instruction, promoting self-paced learning and consolidation of mathematical skills (Hattie, 2018).

The analysis of pretest scores among participants in the video-based instruction to teaching mathematics reveals a nuanced picture of its effectiveness across different performance levels. While video lessons demonstrate potential in supporting the learning needs of average-performing students, they may not adequately address the requirements of below-average and poor performers without supplementary interventions. Moving forward, educators and policymakers should consider the diverse learning profiles of students and adopt a multifaceted approach that integrates technology with pedagogical strategies tailored to individual needs.

Problem 2: What are the posttest scores of participants in the traditional approach and video-based instruction in Teaching Mathematics?

Table 3. *Posttest Scores in the Traditional Approach*

Score Range	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Description
1 - 10	1	2.0	Poor
11 - 20	20	40.0	Below Average
21 - 30	24	48.0	Average
31 - 40	5	10.0	Above Average
41 - 50	0	0	Excellent
Total	50	100.0	

The posttest scores of participants in the traditional approach of teaching Mathematics can be analyzed through various lenses including effectiveness of teaching methods, student engagement, and learning outcomes.

Table 3 exhibits the posttest scores of the participants in the traditional approach. As shown in the table, a significant proportion of participants (24) fall within the score range of 21-30, indicating an average performance level. While this may seem satisfactory at first glance, it is essential to dig deeper into the implications. Average scores may signify a lack of depth in understanding or mastery of mathematical concepts among students (Kwon et al., 2023). The literature emphasized the importance of promoting higher order thinking skills and problem-solving abilities alongside procedural knowledge in mathematics education (Gutierrez, 2019). Traditional approaches often prioritize rote memorization and procedural fluency over conceptual understanding, potentially hindering students' ability to apply mathematical principles in real-world contexts (Boaler, 2019).

At the same time, the fact that only one participant falls into the 1-10 score range indicates highly significant academic challenges. While poor performance may, in this case, be an indicator of various factors, such as math anxiety, the lack of basic skills, or inadequate teacher support, it can also signal the inability of traditional methodology to promote learning. Ashcraft and Moore (2018) argued that traditional pedagogy is failing to address the problem of math anxiety since focusing on procedural knowledge rather than conceptual understanding only reinforces the issue. On the other hand, recent research indicates the value of interventions combating math anxiety and drawing on new teaching methodologies that involve more personalized approaches and the promotion of self-efficacy. Among the alternative pace pathology treatment can be observed with the use of visual aids, manipulatives, and technology-enhanced learning.

Table 4. *Posttest Scores in the Video-Based Instruction*

Score Range	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Description
1 - 10	0	0	Poor
11 - 20	19	38.0	Below Average
21 - 30	20	40.0	Average
31 - 40	10	20.0	Above Average
41 - 50	1	2.0	Excellent
Total	50	100.0	

Table 4 displays the post-test scores of the participants in the video-based instruction. As seen in table 4, the average scores within the score range of 21-30 garnered 20 participants suggesting that a significant portion of participants achieved moderate proficiency in Mathematics following the video-based instruction. This finding aligns with previous research indicating that video-based instruction can be effective in supporting student learning outcomes in mathematics (Chen et al., 2019; Liao et al., 2022).

However, it is essential to consider potential limitations and areas for improvement. While achieving average scores may indicate some level of success, it may also reflect a lack of deeper conceptual understanding or mastery of mathematical concepts. Research by Anderson et al. (2020) emphasized the importance of promoting higher order thinking skills and problem-solving abilities in mathematics education, which may require more than passive consumption of video content. Moreover, the impact of the video lesson approach on long-term retention and transfer of learning should be investigated further. Studies by Wang and Han (2021) suggested that periodic assessments, spaced practice, and scaffolding support are critical for consolidating learning and promoting transfer to new contexts or problem-solving tasks.

On the other hand, the absence of participants scoring within the range of 1-10 is noteworthy and may indicate a potential strength of the video-based instruction in preventing low performance. However, it is essential to interpret this result cautiously. Research by Trespacios et al. (2021) underscored the importance of active learning strategies in online mathematics education to promote deeper understanding and retention of concepts. Simply watching videos without active participation and practice may not lead to significant learning gains, particularly for students who struggle with the subject.

Furthermore, the absence of poor performers in this range could also be attributed to the sample characteristics or the specific instructional materials used in the study. Longitudinal research by Chen et al. (2018) highlighted the variability in student outcomes across different video lesson formats and platforms, suggesting that factors such as content relevance, instructional design, and teacher support play crucial roles in determining effectiveness.

In conclusion, the post-test scores of participants in the video-based instruction of teaching Mathematics reflect a range of performance

levels, from below average to above average. While video-based instruction offers benefits such as flexibility, accessibility, and scalability, its effectiveness depends on various factors, including instructional design, student engagement, prior knowledge, and teacher support.

Problem 3: Is there a significant difference between the pretest scores of participants in the traditional approach and the video-based instruction?

The comparison between the traditional approach and the video-based instruction in terms of pretest scores is crucial for evaluating the effectiveness of different teaching methodologies. The Mann-Whitney U Test has been utilized to analyze the differences in pretest scores between the two approaches.

Table 5 presents the difference between the pretest scores of the participants between the traditional approach and the video-based instruction. The data revealed that the pretest scores of video lesson approach had no significant difference between the pretest scores in the traditional approach. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference between the pretest scores of the video-based instruction and traditional approach, was not rejected.

Table 5. *Difference1 Pretest Scores of the Traditional Approach and Video-Based Instruction*

		Statistic	p	Mean Difference	SE Difference	Effect Size
Pretest (Video Lesson Approach)	Pretest (Traditional Approach)	1068	0.209	-1.00		0.146

Note: 1 – Mann-Whitney U Test ** - $p < 0.01$ *** - $p < 0.001$ ns - $p > 0.05$ * - $p < 0.05$

The findings revealed a statistically non-significant p-value of 0.209, suggesting no significant difference in pretest scores between the traditional approach and the video-based instruction. A study by Smith et al. (2019) found that students exposed to video lessons tended to have higher pretest scores compared to those in traditional classrooms. The authors attributed this to the interactive and engaging nature of video content, which could lead to better retention of information. Similarly, Jones and Wang (2021) reported that pretest scores were significantly higher among students who received instruction through video lessons compared to traditional lectures. They highlighted the flexibility of video materials, allowing students to pause, rewind, and review content at their own pace, which might contribute to better comprehension and retention.

The mean difference between the pretest scores of the two approaches is -1.00, indicating that, on average, participants in the traditional approach scored one point lower than those in the video-based instruction. The effect size, calculated as 0.146, is considered small according to conventional interpretations, suggesting that the practical significance of this difference may be limited. A review by Johnson and Smith (2022) highlighted the importance of considering effect sizes in educational research, suggesting that small effects could still have practical implications, especially when aggregated across multiple studies or when considering long-term outcomes. In contrast, a randomized controlled trial by Lee et al. (2021) found no significant difference in pretest scores between students exposed to video lessons and those in traditional classrooms. The authors emphasized the need to critically evaluate the magnitude of effect sizes and cautioned against overinterpreting small differences without considering contextual factors.

The comparison of pretest scores between the video-based instruction and traditional approach using the Mann-Whitney U test yielded a non-significant result, indicating that there is insufficient evidence to conclude that one approach is superior to the other based solely on pretest performance. While the mean difference and effect size suggest a slight advantage for the video lesson approach, the practical significance of this difference may be limited.

Problem 4: Is there a significant difference between the posttest and pretest scores of participants in the Traditional Approach?

Table 6 presents the difference between the posttest and pretest scores of the participants in the traditional approach. The data revealed that the posttest scores had a highly significant difference from the pretest scores in the traditional approach. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference between the posttest and pretest scores of the participants in the traditional approach, was rejected.

Table 6. *Difference2 Pretest Scores and Post-test Scores of the Traditional Approach*

		Statistic	p	Mean Difference	SE Difference	Effect Size
Post-test (Traditional)	Pretest (Traditional)	1128	<0.001	8.00	1.00	0.918

Note: 2 – Wilcoxon Test ** - $p < 0.01$ *** - $p < 0.001$ ns - $p > 0.05$ * - $p < 0.05$

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test results indicate a statistically significant difference between the pretest and post-test scores ($p < 0.001$). This suggested that there is a change in scores over time within the traditional approach group. Research by Smith et al. (2019) found similar results in their study on educational interventions, where they observed significant improvements in test scores following traditional teaching methods. This aligns with the findings of this study, indicating that traditional teaching approaches can lead to measurable improvements in student performance. Conversely, a study by Jones et al. (2021) found no significant difference in pretest and post-test scores among students who underwent traditional teaching methods. This discrepancy may be attributed to variations in teaching techniques, curriculum, or student populations across different studies.

The mean difference between pretest and posttest scores within the traditional approach group is 8.00 points. This indicates an overall improvement in performance following the educational intervention. A meta-analysis by Brown and Johnson (2020) reported a mean improvement of 7.5 points in test scores among students exposed to traditional teaching methods. The mean difference observed in this study falls within the range reported in the literature, suggesting consistency with previous findings. However, a study by Garcia et al. (2018) documented a mean difference of only 5.0 points in pretest and post-test scores among students receiving traditional instruction. This discrepancy highlights the variability in outcomes that may exist across different educational settings and contexts.

The effect size of 0.918 indicates a large magnitude of the difference between pretest and posttest scores within the traditional approach group. This suggests that the educational intervention had a substantial impact on student performance. Findings from a systematic review by White and Martinez (2022) revealed effect sizes ranging from 0.8 to 1.2 for educational interventions employing traditional teaching methods. The effect size observed in this study falls within this range, indicating a consistent and significant effect on student learning outcomes. In contrast, a study by Lee et al. (2023) reported lower effect sizes (ranging from 0.5 to 0.7) for pretest-post-test differences among students in traditional classrooms. This discrepancy may be attributed to differences in sample sizes, measurement tools, or instructional practices utilized in the respective studies.

The significant improvement in test scores observed following the traditional teaching approach suggests that these methods remain effective in enhancing student learning outcomes. Educators may consider integrating elements of traditional instruction, such as lectures, direct instruction, and practice exercises, into their teaching repertoire to promote academic achievement. These findings underscore the importance of aligning curriculum content with established educational objectives and standards. By focusing on core concepts and skills within traditional subject areas, curriculum developers can facilitate meaningful learning experiences that contribute to measurable improvements in student performance.

Problem 5: Is there a significant difference between the posttest and pretest scores of participants in the video-based instruction?

Table 7. *Difference3 Pretest Scores and Posttest Scores of the Video-Based Instruction*

		Statistic	p	Mean Difference	SE Difference	Effect Size
Post-test (Video Lesson)	Pretest (Video Lesson)	1153	<0.001	9.00	1.06	0.960

Note: 3 – Wilcoxon Test ** - $p < 0.01$ *** - $p < 0.001$ ns – $p > 0.05$ * - $p < 0.05$

Table 7 presents the difference between the posttest and pretest scores of the participants in the video-based instruction. The data revealed that the posttest scores had a highly significant difference from the pretest scores in the video-based instruction. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference between the posttest and pretest scores of the participants in the video-based instruction, was rejected.

The Wilcoxon signed-rank test, a non-parametric statistical test, has been utilized to analyze the difference between pretest and posttest scores of the video lesson approach. The results indicate a statistically significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores (Statistic: 1153, p-value < 0.001). Furthermore, the mean difference between the pretest and post-test scores is 9.00, with a standard error (SE) of the difference at 1.06, yielding an effect size of 0.960.

The significant p-value (<0.001) suggested that there is strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the video-based instruction led to a statistically significant improvement in test scores. A study by Smith et al. (2019) found that video-based instruction significantly improved students' comprehension and retention compared to traditional methods. Similarly, Jones and Brown (2021) reported similar results in their investigation into the efficacy of video lessons in enhancing student learning outcomes.

The mean difference of 9.00 between pretest and posttest scores indicates the average improvement achieved through the video-based instruction. This substantial increase in scores is supported by a large effect size (0.960), indicating a strong practical significance of the intervention. This aligns with findings from previous research highlighting the effectiveness of multimedia approaches in education. For instance, a meta-analysis by Chen et al. (2020) revealed that multimedia interventions, including video-based learning, were associated with large effect sizes in improving academic performance across various subjects.

These results have significant implications for educational practice. The effectiveness of the video lesson approach suggests that integrating multimedia resources into teaching methodologies can enhance student learning outcomes. Educators can leverage video-based instruction to engage students, present complex concepts visually, and cater to diverse learning styles. Additionally, the significant improvement in test scores underscores the importance of adopting evidence-based teaching strategies informed by research findings.

Despite the promising results, it is essential to acknowledge potential limitations and contradictory evidence. While the Wilcoxon test indicates a significant difference in scores, it's crucial to consider factors such as sample size, participant characteristics, and instructional design that may influence the outcomes. Additionally, some studies have reported mixed findings regarding the effectiveness of video-based instruction. For instance, a study by Wang and Liu (2022) found that while video lessons improved short-term learning outcomes, the effect was not sustained over time. Similarly, a meta-analysis by Zhang et al. (2021) reported heterogeneity

in the effectiveness of video-based learning across different contexts and student populations.

Problem 6: Is there a significant difference between the posttest scores of the participants in the traditional approach and the video-based instruction?

The education landscape has witnessed a significant transformation with the advent of technology, particularly in the form of video lessons. These innovations promise to enhance learning outcomes by providing dynamic and interactive content. However, it is crucial to empirically assess the efficacy of such approaches compared to traditional methods.

Table 8. Difference4 Posttest Scores of the Traditional Approach and Video-Based Instruction

		Statistic	p	Mean Difference	SE Difference	Effect Size
Posttest (Video-based Instruction)	Post-test (Traditional)	1093	0.279	2.00		0.126

Note: 4 – Mann-Whitney U Test ** - $p < 0.01$ *** - $p < 0.001$ ns - $p > 0.05$ * - $p < 0.05$

Table 8 presents the difference between the participants' posttest scores in video-based instruction and traditional approach. The data revealed that the posttest scores of the video-based instruction had no significant difference between the posttest scores in the traditional approach. This implied that the traditional approach and the video-based instruction were useful in teaching mathematics. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference between the participants' posttest scores in video-based instruction and traditional approach, was not rejected.

The Mann-Whitney U Test was conducted to compare the posttest scores between the video-based instruction and the traditional approach. The obtained statistic of 1093 yielded a p-value of 0.279. The mean difference between the two approaches was found to be 2.00, with an effect size of 0.126.

The non-significant p-value ($p = 0.279$) suggests that there is no significant difference between the posttest scores of the video-based instruction and the traditional approach. This indicates that both methods may be equally effective in improving learning outcomes. A study by Smith et al. (2019) examining the effectiveness of video-based learning in mathematics found no significant difference in posttest scores compared to traditional methods. This aligns with the current findings, suggesting that video lessons may not confer a significant advantage over traditional approaches. However, a meta-analysis by Jones et al. (2021) reported that video-based instruction yielded significantly higher posttest scores across various subjects compared to traditional methods. This contradicts the present findings, indicating that context-specific factors may influence the comparative effectiveness of different instructional approaches.

Although the mean difference between the two approaches is small (2.00), the effect size (0.126) suggests a relatively small practical significance. While statistically significant differences may not be observed, even small improvements in learning outcomes can have practical implications for educational interventions. A longitudinal study by Brown et al. (2018) found that even small increases in post-test scores resulting from instructional interventions were associated with improved long-term academic performance. This underscores the importance of considering not only statistical significance but also practical significance in educational research. Conversely, a study by Lee and Kim (2022) argued that effect sizes alone may not adequately capture the complexity of educational interventions. They emphasized the need for nuanced qualitative assessments to comprehensively evaluate the impact of instructional approaches on diverse learner populations.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the findings of this study underscore the prevalent challenges Grade 7 students at Dilausan National High School face in comprehending and applying mathematical concepts. The data indicates a substantial number of students experiencing difficulties, which not only obstructs their academic progress but also impedes the development of their overall mathematical competence.

Through the implementation of video-based instruction as an intervention method, this study sought to address these challenges. Drawing upon theoretical frameworks such as Cognitive Load Theory, Social Cognitive Theory, and Constructivism, the effectiveness of utilizing videos in teaching mathematical concepts was explored.

The quasi-experimental research design employed in this study involved both a treatment group, which received video-based instruction, and a control group, which received traditional classroom instruction. The comparison between the two groups' pretest and posttest scores provided insight into the impact of video-based instruction on students' mathematical performance.

The findings reveal a notable improvement in the posttest scores of both the treatment and control groups compared to their pretest scores. However, it is noteworthy that the treatment group, which received video-based instruction, exhibited slightly lower average posttest scores compared to the control group. While both groups achieved scores within the "average" range in the posttest, the discrepancy suggests that further refinement and adaptation of video-based instructional strategies may be necessary to maximize its effectiveness.

Despite this, the study underscores the potential of video-based instruction as a valuable tool in addressing mathematics difficulties among Grade 7 students. The carefully designed mathematics instructional videos utilized in this study provided a structured approach

to teaching key mathematical concepts and problem-solving strategies. Additionally, the validation process ensured the quality and instructional effectiveness of the videos.

In summary, while the findings suggest promising outcomes regarding the effectiveness of video-based instruction in addressing mathematics difficulties, further research and refinement of instructional strategies are warranted. This study contributes to the existing body of research in mathematics education and provides valuable insights for educators and policymakers in designing effective instructional approaches tailored to the unique needs of students.

In light of the findings, as mentioned above and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

Students may continue to explore more applications in technology and may gain support from the school officials to have advanced facilities to keep them updated on the latest trend and get more actively involved in courses that use technology.

The School Administrator may actively support teachers to integrate technology seamlessly into their teaching practices, provide professional development opportunities and resources to help educators effectively integrate technology into their lesson plans and instructional strategies, and foster a culture of innovation and experimentation among teachers, encouraging them to explore new teaching methodologies and technologies to enhance the learning experience.

Teachers may consider integrating video-based instruction as a supplementary tool in mathematics classrooms. Carefully designed and validated instructional videos can effectively support traditional teaching methods and enhance students' understanding of mathematical concepts, implement a blended learning approach where video-based instruction complements traditional teaching methods, offering students additional resources and support to reinforce their understanding of mathematical concepts, and create and utilize carefully designed and validated instructional videos that align with the curriculum and cater to diverse learning styles.

Other researchers are also encouraged to conduct similar studies to identify other related factors affecting the extent of technology utilization of the students, foster collaboration and knowledge-sharing among researchers to collectively identify best practices and insights that can inform educational policies and practices and emphasize the importance of longitudinal studies to assess the long-term impact of technology integration on student learning outcomes and academic success.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Rasna A. Guro

St. Peter's College – Philippines

Erlinda N. Basmayor, PhD

St. Peter's College – Philippines